

Understanding teaching methods

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Annotatsiya: Talabalarda matematika o'qitish metodikasida qo'llaniladigan o'qitish metodlari haqidagi bilim, malaka va ko'nikmalarini mustahkamlash. Boshlang'ich matematika ta'limi jarayonida o'rganilgan o'qitish metodlarini tadbqiq eta bilishni o'rgatish.

Kalit so'zlar: Metod, o'qitish metodi, og'zaki, amaliy, ko'rsatmalilik.

Аннотация: Закрепление знаний, навыков и умений учащихся о методах обучения, используемых в методике преподавания математики. Обучение умению применять методы обучения, изученные в ходе начального математического образования.

Ключевые слова: метод, метод обучения, устный, практический, инструктивный.

Abstract: Strengthening students' knowledge, skills and abilities about teaching methods used in mathematics teaching methodology. Teaching the ability to apply teaching methods learned in the course of primary mathematics education.

Key words: Method, teaching method, oral, practical, instructional.

The concept of teaching method is one of the basic concepts of didactics and

methodology. Scholars have given different definitions to the term "learning method". The teaching method is a joint activity of a teacher and a student, in exchange for which students acquire knowledge, skills and abilities. The worldview of students is being formed, they are preparing for life and work. Thus, teaching methods perform three main tasks: mastery, education and development. It is necessary to study the classification of all teaching methods in order to consciously choose from teaching methods those that correspond to the new content and new tasks of education. In research on the methodology of mathematics, other methods are also used. Usually, the combined use of all these methods ensures the reliability of the results. In modern didactics, there are different approaches to the classification of teaching methods.

Based on their different attitudes towards the method, they gave different definitions of the method itself. For example: LN Skatkin defines the method. "Teaching methodology is one of the ways to organize the cognitive activity of students in the classroom." Strong psychologist I. Ya. Lerner agrees with this opinion. In addition, the methodologist Nekandarov in his doctoral dissertation defines teaching methods: "Teaching methods are ways of initiating learning activities in students in a given lesson." But later, in a book on pedagogy by G. I. Shchukina, a detailed description of teaching methods was given. "Teaching method is a joint activity of a teacher and students aimed at achieving learning goals in a given lesson." This definition is somewhat complete and perfect.

Because the activities of the teacher and the student are considered together

in the method. Or the Department of Biology of the Scientific Research Institute in Moscow defines the content and methods of teaching as follows: “The method of teaching is the organized work of the teacher and students in the classroom, in exchange for which educational work is carried out. be solved” is determined according to the methods of teaching in the primary education sector at that institution. “The method of teaching is the joint activity of the teacher and students in this lesson, in exchange for which knowledge, skills, and abilities are given. worldview is formed. An element of independence arises in students, they prepare for life and work.

In our opinion, the most appropriate is a classification that includes various methods. There are different approaches to the classification of teaching methods, and the most adequate classification, including various methods, is the classification given by Academician Y. Babansky. In general, as we saw above, teaching methods consist of the joint activity of the teacher and students. Therefore, such activities involve organization, promotion and control.

In conclusion, we can say that teaching methods consist of joint activities of the teacher and students. Therefore, the organization of such activities involves stimulation and control, respectively, teaching methods are divided into three large groups: methods of organizing educational activities; methods of stimulating educational activity; methods of monitoring the effectiveness of educational activities.

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